

MADANIY XABARDORLIKNI OSHIRISH VA EKOLOGIK BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH | xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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«Og‘ir ekologik sharoitga qaramasdan, mamlakatimiz taraqqiyotiga munosib hissa qo‘shib kelayotgan Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini, uning barcha shahar, tuman va ovullarini kompleks tarzda rivojlantirish, mehnatkash va matonatli, oqko‘ngil va bag‘rikeng qoraqalpoq elining hayotini obod va farovon etishga har qachongidan ham ustuvor ahamiyat qaratamiz.

Bizning oliy va ezgu maqsadimiz – birgalikdagi fidokorona mehnatimiz bilan Yangi O‘zbekiston tarkibida Yangi Qoraqalpog‘istonni bunyod etishdir.»

Sh.M.MIRZIYOYEV
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti

Prezident: “Bu ko‘prik o‘zbek va qoraqalpoq xalqlari o‘rtasidagi og‘zibirlik va hamkorlik ko‘prigidir”.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini Xorazm viloyati bilan bog‘lovchi ko‘prik. Asosiy qo‘shma ko‘prikning uzunligi 413 metr bo‘lib, eni 8 metr; har bir oralig‘i 66 metrni tashkil qiladi. Uning 7 ta ustuni 6 ta oraliqqa o‘rnatilgan.

KIRISH

2024-yilning 17–18-may kunlari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi Xo‘jayli tumanida o‘tkazilgan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy madaniy, etnografik va ekologik merosini keng jamoatchilikka tanitishda hamda turizm infratuzilmalarini mustahkamlashda muhim qadam bo‘ldi

Anjumanning asosiy maqsadi Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozoriga olib kirish va madaniy xabardorlikni oshirishdir. Qoraqalpog‘iston o‘zining tarixiy boyliklari, arxeologik yodgorliklari va o‘ziga xos tabiiy manzaralari bilan dunyo sayyohlarini jalb etadigan katta jozibadorlikka ega. Bu hududda jahon madaniy va tabiiy merosi obyektlariga mansub ko‘plab joylar mavjud bo‘lib, ularning aksariyati turizm infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishga asos bo‘ladi.

Xususan, Qoraqalpog‘istondagi insoniyat tamaddunidan hikoya qiluvchi arxeologik yodgorliklar bisyor. Hozirgi kunda Qoraqalpog‘istonda 300 dan ortiq arxeologik obyektlar mavjud bo‘lib, ulardan eng mashhurlari – Ko‘hna Urganch, Tupraqal‘a, Ellikqal‘a va Ayoqal‘a hududlaridagi qadimiy manzillardir. Bular, o‘z navbatida, sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirib, hududning turistik imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha muhokamalar o‘tkazildi. Birinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalariga bag‘ishlanib, mahalliy infratuzilmalarni takomillashtirish hamda turizm xizmatlarini kengaytirish bo‘yicha takliflar ishlab chiqildi. Ikkinchi yo‘nalishda etnografik turizmni rivojlantirish, xususan, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni targ‘ib etish va milliy madaniy boyliklarni namoyish qilish masalalari muhokama qilindi. Uchinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari orqali targ‘ib qilish masalalariga bag‘ishlandi.

Ushbu anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish yo‘lida muhim qadamdir. Turizm, madaniy meros va ekologik yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan taklif va tavsiyalar hududni xalqaro turistik xaritada o‘z o‘rniga ega bo‘lishiga yordam beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi tarixiy, madaniy va tabiiy boyliklarga ega hudud sifatida nafaqat O‘zbekiston, balki butun Markaziy Osiyoda alohida o‘rin tutadi. Bu hududni «ochiq osmon ostidagi arxeologik muzey» deb atash mumkin, chunki bu yerda qadimiy Xorazm madaniyatining markazi bo‘lgan Qoraqalpog‘istonda nafaqat arxeologik meros, balki etnografik va ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish uchun katta imkoniyatlar mavjud.

Qoraqalpog‘istonda o‘tkaziladigan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro anjuman ana

shunday salohiyatni namoyon etish va rivojlantirish maqsadida tashkil etilgan. Anjuman doirasida turli olimlar, tadqiqotchilar va xalqaro ekspertlar ishtirokida ekologik barqarorlik va madaniy merosni saqlash masalalari muhokama qilinib, zamonaviy turizm yo‘nalishlaridagi ilmiy-nazariy takliflar ishlab chiqildi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha quyidagi muhokamalar o‘tkazildi:

- *Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalari;*
- *Etnografik turizmni tashkil etishning asosiy xususiyatlari;*
- *Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida targ‘ib qilishning zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari.*

Anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida ekologik va etnografik turizm nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga tanitishga yordam berishi olgari surildi.

Anjumanda xalqaro institutlar vakillarining qatnashishi bejiz emas. Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy tarixi va Xorazm madaniyati bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan qadimiy yodgorliklar va arxeologik topinmalar bu hududni nafaqat tarixchilar, arxeologlar uchun, balki turistlar uchun ham jozibadorligini oshirib boradi.

Masalan, Ko‘kcha III qabristoni – qadimgi bronza davri madaniyatiga oid yodgorlik bo‘lib, millioddan avvalgi XIII-XI asrlarga oid, deb taxmin qilinadi. Bu madaniyatlar ko‘p asrlar davomida bir-biri bilan hamkorlikda yashaganini va turli etnik guruhlarining madaniy merosini o‘zida mujassam etganini ko‘rsatadi.

Masalan, S.P. Tolstov¹ tomonidan o‘rganilgan Tazabagyab madaniyatlari ham Qoraqalpog‘istonning arxeologik salohiyatining muhim qismi bo‘lib, ularni o‘rganish natijasida bronza davrining ikki madaniyati bir vaqtning o‘zida mavjud bo‘lgani ma‘lum bo‘lgan. Bu esa hududda turli tarixiy etnik va madaniy jarayonlar sodir bo‘lganidan dalolat beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘istonning ushbu yodgorliklari va arxeologik manzillari sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirishi mumkin.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasining turizm salohiyati juda katta bo‘lib, uni jahon turizm bozoriga zamonaviy marketing vositalari orqali chiqarish imkoni bor. Bu borada ekologik va etnografik turizm muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu turizm yo‘nalishlari nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki uning madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga yoyishda ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mazkur anjuman, ayniqsa, Qoraqalpog‘istonning kelgusi turizm salohiyatini mustahkamlashda, asosiy yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan takliflarni keng tatbiq qilishda omil bo‘lib, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirish va yangi turizm xizmatlarini joriy qilishga, hudud aholisi uchun yetarli darajada doimiy va mavsumiy daromadli ish o‘rinlari yaratishga xizmat qiladi.

1 <https://ensiklopediya.uz>

II-SHO'BA

Etnografik turizmni
tashkil etishning
asosiy xususiyatlari

Shameka Fernander
Director Of Operations
at Moosaic Finance,
Bahamas

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

SUSTAINABLE PATHWAYS: BALANCING NATURE AND BUSINESS

The Bahamas, officially known as the Commonwealth of The Bahamas, is an archipelago consisting of more than 700 islands, and cays. It is situated north of Cuba and southeast of the Florida USA. Of the 700, about 20 islands are inhabited, each creating an isolated yet interconnected ecosystem that supports a rich diversity of life.

Marine ecosystems dominate the Bahamian environment, featuring some of the clearest waters on the planet. Coral reefs thrive here, supporting a multitude of fish species, sea turtles, and marine mammals in a vibrant underwater landscape that attracts

Today, I am excited to share with you a little about the vibrant world of eco-tourism in the Bahamas. As a Bahamian living in Uzbekistan, I have witnessed firsthand the transformative power of tourism that respects and preserves its environment and culture.

snorkelers and divers from around the world. The islands are also surrounded by shallow seas, which are critical habitats for the breeding and nursery grounds of both commercial and game fish.

This rich mix of marine and terrestrial ecosystems not only makes the Bahamas a beautiful and intriguing place to visit but also a critical area for biodiversity and ecological research.

Tourism is the heartbeat of the Bahamian economy, contributing to over 50% of the country's GDP and employing over 65% of the workforce. In The Bahamas, eco-tourism revolves significantly around marine conservation. A pivotal component of our tourism strategy is emphasizing environmental sustainability and the enhancement of visitor experiences through educational and participatory activities.

As a low-lying archipelago, we face significant risks from rising sea levels a direct consequence of climate change. The effects of climate change impact us the most, even though we contribute to it the least.

The primary risks are beach erosion, coral reef degradation, and increased hurricane activity.

One of the cornerstone strategies of Bahamian ecotourism is the establishment marine protected areas (MPA's). These projects are a collaboration between government stakeholders, private sector businesses and NGOs, designed to promote and advance sustainable tourism practices.

Two of the most popular marine protected areas are

1. Andros Barrier Reef Protection: At over 200 kilometers long, the Andros Barrier Reef is the third-longest barrier reef in the world. This vital ecosystem is home to 164 species of fish and coral. Guided snorkeling and diving tours bring in over \$150 million a year for the local economy in Andros.

2. Exuma Cays Land and Sea Park: was the first land and sea park in the world covers 455 square kilometers. The park is home to a wide variety of marine species, including fish, corals, sea turtles, and other marine organisms. It's breathtaking beauty and safe anchorages made it a very popular boating spot in The Bahamas, welcoming thousands of boaters every year. Its healthy ecosystems and proper fisheries management made it an ideal spot for researchers and scientists to conduct various types of research.

I'd like to share a personal story: a story about a businessman and a farmer with a deep love for the earth. Seventy years ago, my grandfather Edwin founded Edwin's Fishing Lake in Eleuthera, Bahamas. The lake is a unique 68-acre inland saltwater lake that is connected to the ocean by underground tunnels. His dream was to develop the lake into a reservoir of marine life that was sheltered from the predatory and unfriendly elements

of the open sea. The lake was devoid of life so he populated the lake with over 20,000 fish of 32 varieties.

His dedication didn't stop with fish; he had a special affection for the endangered green sea turtles. To aid their reproduction, he cleared a 100-foot strip of mangroves and imported sand along a section of the shoreline to create a turtle-egg laying beach. Once the eggs hatched, he reared the baby turtles in a small rock-lined alcove and when large enough, he released some into the lake, some into the ocean and sold the rest.

My grandfather envisioned the lake as an environmentally friendly tourist attraction, coining the slogan, «Enjoyable entertainment for tourists and sportsmen.» The pristine marine environment of the lake remains free from plastics, fishing nets, and other pollutants harmful to sea turtles and their prey. The surrounding mangrove habitats not only support a diverse bird population but also provide crucial structural protection to the shoreline.

He devoted his life to the lake until his passing in 1982. Unfortunately, by then, most of his 14 children had moved away, and over the next three decades, the economic use of the lake diminished, with much of the turtles being poached by locals. But luckily because he had placed all types of sea life in the lake, it created a balanced ecosystem where each species could contribute and flourish. The lake has not been stocked with fish for decades, thus remaining species are sustained solely by the natural environments of the lake.

Ten years ago, my family decided to honor my grandfather's legacy by reviving the use and protection of the lake by combining conservation efforts with sustainable income sources to manage the reserve. Our first step was to have the area around the lake officially designated as a marine reserve to safeguard its fragile ecosystem and the species that depend on it. It is now called «Edwin's Turtle Lake Marine Reserve».

We collaborated with conservation researchers and scientists to develop a sustainable eco-tourism business plan, creating income-generating opportunities through minimally invasive, eco-friendly activities such as kayaking, paddle boarding, bird watching, turtle watching, and catch-and-release fishing.

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi

Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана

Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

Our conservation efforts focused on:

- Protecting juvenile sea turtles: Following in my grandfather's footsteps, we restored the turtle egg laying beach.
- Education and awareness: We built a resources center to serve as an educational site for both locals and tourists, highlighting the importance of marine conservation and the specific needs of sea turtles.
- Research: Turtle Lake also presents a unique opportunity to the sea turtle research community. To date, most research is concentrated on nesting females and their migratory patterns. The reserve offers a semi-controlled natural environment for scientists to study sea turtle behavior, growth, and survival strategies.

In contrast to The Bahamas, Uzbekistan's eco-tourism focuses on its vast deserts, mountainous regions, and rich historical sites. Comparing the two countries offer insights into how geographic and cultural differences shape eco-tourism practices. Both regions require tailored strategies that respect their unique environmental and socio-economic contexts to ensure that eco-tourism contributes positively to sustainable development.

Sustainable tourism involves:

1. Environmental Conservation aimed at minimizing the carbon footprint of travel and the degradation of natural environments.
2. Community Involvement: For tourism to be truly sustainable, it must benefit the local community directly. Residents must be at the forefront of the tourism strategy. Tourists are increasingly seeking authentic experiences, and who better to provide these than the local inhabitants themselves?
3. Education and Awareness: Sustainable tourism should aim not only to entertain but also to enlighten. Education is pivotal. Educating tourists about the local environment and cultural practices can greatly enhance their experience and promote respectful behavior.

Eco-tourism represents a profound commitment to preserving our planet's natural beauty and cultural heritage. It is a pathway that offers economic opportunities while safeguarding our environment.

It has been a privilege to share insights on how ecotourism in the Bahamas not only protects the environment but also enriches both the visitor experience and the local economy. I am inspired by our shared commitment to preserving our planet and promoting responsible and sustainable tourism practices.

Each of us has a role to play in protecting our planet. By supporting sustainable tourism and conservation projects, we are investing in the future of our environment and our global community. We are not just visitors on this earth; we are its guardians.

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

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